

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Decision makers				x		
Officers/technicians		x				
Researchers		x				
Private partners	x					
Municipalities			x		x	
General Public						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	LEU_UHI_01
Name	Automated classification of hyper-spectral images for the identification of surface materials, and identification of heat islands in Leuven.
Description	A process and identified machine learning algorithms to classify surface materials from hyperspectral imagery. The output is used, together with other datasets to identify hot spots and priority areas in the city.
Primary User	Data technicians, researchers, municipality
Goal	Provide new data for research and other projects dealing with green deal challenges. This includes surface materials, hotspots mapping and vulnerability index based on urban heat island maps, local population and environmental factors.
Owner	KU Leuven, City of Leuven
Status	Under development
Policy context	

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

<p>Challenges & Priorities</p>	<p>By 2100, the annual average temperature in Belgium will be between 0.7 and 7.2 °C higher than it was around 2000. There will also be more tropical days, with temperatures above 30°C, and heat waves are expected to be more common. Due to the dense construction and the use of heat-absorbing materials, such as concrete and asphalt, cities in Flanders including Leuven, will increasingly suffer from heat stress.</p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The multi-year plan 2020 - 2025 of the city of Leuven: The multi-year policy plan 2020-2025 of the city describes the city’s objectives and plans during the current legislative term: https://leuven.be/sites/leuven.be/files/documents/2019-10/baanbrekend_leuven_-_bestuursnota_2019-2025.pdf. <p>In the multi-year plan, the city of Leuven expresses its overall ambition to become a careful, green and prosperous city. The multi-year plan is structured around ten specific ambitions which are translated into programmes. Among these ten programmes, which are further detailed into action programmes, there is a programme on a ‘Sustainable, climate resilient and circular city’, which relates with “the challenge of moving towards a sustainable, climate-neutral society, while keeping in mind the social aspect”.</p> <p>In order to reduce heat islands during the summer months, the city will set up projects integrating different types of measures, such as softening and infiltration measures, water buffering, shadow trees and green roofs and green facades. Given the importance of large voluminous trees, the city is particularly committed to the preservation of trees in the urban area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (2019) Leuven 2030 Roadmap 2025 · 2035 · 2050: A co-created roadmap to climate neutrality by 2050, formally endorsed by 15 key stakeholders and outlining actions across 10 thematic and three cross-cutting programs (including Scope 3 emissions): https://roadmap-en.leuven2030.be/ <p>The Roadmap consists of thirteen programs on themes such as energy, mobility and climate adaptation, each containing several specific climate actions, which citizens, organisations and governments can take to contribute to help the city towards climate neutrality. One of these programs is focused on the “Green and resilient city”, stating that “regardless of whether or not Leuven achieves the goal of climate neutrality by 2050, additional measures will be required to cope with the effects of climate change. Such adaptive measures have the added benefit of enhancing the city’s quality of life”.</p> <p>The programme on ‘Green and resilient city’ of the Leuven 2030 Roadmap has a specific section (a so-called ‘site’) on combating the heat island effect. While more frequent and longer heat waves are rather unpleasant to city residents, they also cause an increase in mortality rates, reduce work</p>

	<p>performance, increase energy consumption for cooling etc. That is why the city wants to combat the heat island effects, through a series of measures and solutions. Important to note is that many of these measures and solutions are also relevant for other purposes (or other areas of climate policy): softening of soils, more afforestation, (urban) ventilation, the presence of water and the choice of materials in the built space.</p> <p>Some additional measures specifically focused on heat island effects are proposed. For instance, in all spatial projects, the impact on heat island effects should be assessed and taken into consideration. Specific projects should be undertaken, like planting large- trees in public spaces, realising green roofs and green facades and reducing the amount of paving in the city. The Roadmap has a clear target to assess the impact of these measures: in 2035 the temperature difference between the city and the surrounding area should be limited to a maximum of 2° C.</p>
Local Green Deal / City contract(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (2021) Climate Action Plan 2020-2025: A plan aligned to the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan that defines actions across 10 domains, identifies action owners, and establishes time frames for implementation: https://www.leuven.be/klimaatactieplan <p>In its Climate Action Plan the City of Leuven recognises heat stress as an important risk of climate change in the city, especially in heavily hardened neighbourhoods where at-risk groups live. The so-called blue-green structure in the city is an important element in increasing the city's resilience, as it is essential to the quality of life in the city: it protects the city against the effects of global warming, contributes to the quality of life and biodiversity, enhances the mental and physical health of the citizens and provides a place for agriculture, nature and recreation.</p> <p>The Climate Action Plan contains a dedicated set of measures and actions related to heat islands, and heat control in general, through which the city wants to minimise and even reduce the impact of the heat island effect. Among these measures is the use of building materials and construction techniques that avoid heat absorption as much as possible. Also the creation of shadow and integration of cooling elements in the city centre are important measures. In (re-)designing the public domain, heat islands will be considered as a determining factor. Especially in those areas that are revealed as priority areas in vulnerability analyses, measures such as the creation of shadow areas through planting trees and the use of materials that mitigate heat islands will be considered.</p> <p>Citizens in Leuven can receive free, customised advice about energy-efficient construction or renovation works from a so-called 'energy coach'. This coach will provide them with answers to questions such as "How do you start an energy-efficient renovation?" and "Is my roof suitable for solar panels?". The city's energy coaches will also take into</p>

	<p>consideration heat island effects in their advice to citizens. This also is the case for citizen engagement campaigns, such as biodiversity campaigns or campaigns on neighbourhood initiatives, where heat island effects also will be taken into consideration in the design and implementation stages.</p> <p>The development of a city heat plan is also considered as an important mechanism. This heat plan will contain both structural measures to counter the effect of heat islands but also temporary measures that can be taken during heat waves. Examples of such measures are the creation of temporary shadow spaces, the provision of buildings, the opening of private areas or parks, etc. The city heat plan will take into consideration results and findings from relevant projects and studies on this topic. Moreover, the plan will also look into communication actions to be rolled out in case of heat waves.</p> <p>In addition, there are various measures related to green management and water management in the city, which – as a co-benefit – also mitigate the heat island effect in the city.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (2023) Climate City Contract: Being one of the 100 cities selected by the European Commission for the mission '100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030', the city together with Leuven 2030 developed the first Leuven climate contract, which contains different innovative breakthrough projects and associated commitments from partners from the entire Leuven society. leuven_nzc_ccc_ok.pdf (netzerocities.app) <p>The action plan - which is part of the Climate City Contract - focuses on five major – emission - domains: renewable energy, buildings, transport and mobility, green infrastructure and circular economy and waste.</p> <p>Addressing heat stress and heat islands is covered under the - emission - domain of 'Nature-Based Solutions and Green Infrastructure'. Typically, they are considered as part of an integrated approach on NbS and climate action in general.</p>
<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p><i>This use case contributes to increasing the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; and achieving the priorities related to climate adaptation. The EU Strategy for Adaptation sets both the framework for achieving climate neutrality and the ambition on adaptation by 2050. The implementation of these actions aims to respond to the needs of adaptation to climate change at the local level and the reduction of the impact of increasingly persistent hazards such as the rising urban temperatures.</i></p>
<p>Precondition</p>	
<p>Input data: Hyperspectral images, Thermal Images, LST, Weather stations, Population data Tools: Classification algorithms, FBK_UHI tool, FBK_Vulnerability</p>	

Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<p><i>Surface materials dataset:</i> https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/200b7e3e-4e79-4300-ab9d-e63ebea05974</p> <p><i>Air temperature raster:</i> https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/c4548cee-2ede-4065-946e-f1ad4dfd8f1b</p> <p><i>Vulnerability Index map:</i> https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6f454b69-57f3-49a2-ae08-47aadf03435a</p>
Use of DRI	<p>The surface materials dataset provides information to the city about the constitution of materials in the built environment of Leuven. This provides an important base layer for further UHI investigations like hotspot detection and vulnerability mapping, as well as use-cases in other policy areas.</p> <p>An air temperature map generated identifies urban heat islands based on surface materials, and a combination of other datasets namely LST, and weather stations data.</p> <p>Vulnerability index map, which adds socio-economic components of the population to hotspot mapping, will help to identify priority areas for intervention actions for the city. This can be used to guide nature-based solutions locations.</p>
Use case processing steps	
UC_LEU-UHI_BPMN_Updated.drawio - draw.io (diagrams.net)	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118423	